

FORS

explore.understand.share.

FORS - Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences

Overview of the services offered to the researchers

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FORS

Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences

What we do

Infrastructure

Data production

Research

Collaboration

Developments

What we offer

Archiving service

Data distribution

Support

Survey mandates

Dissemination of information

FORS – Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences

- Research infrastructure of national scope intended for any institution or person active in the social sciences in Switzerland
- Funded by the Swiss Confederation and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), hosted at the University of Lausanne
- Founded in 2008 by merging existing entities (SIDOS, SHP, Selects)

Infrastructures for data and researchers

FORSbase

An online tool for archiving and distributing research data. Most comprehensive catalogue of social science research projects.

SwissUbase

A national cross-disciplinary solution for Swiss universities and other research organisations based on FORSbase *(in development)*

Linkhub

Centre dedicated to data linking *(in development)*

Data production

Schweizer Haushalt-Panel
Panel suisse de ménages
Swiss Household Panel

European
Social
Survey

Selects Swiss
Election
Study

European *Values* Study

VOTO

 SHARE SURVEY OF HEALTH, AGEING
AND RETIREMENT IN EUROPE

 ISSP

+ Other ad hoc
surveys

Research

What we offer

Archiving service

Preservation of Swiss social science research data

Data distribution

Access to archived data at FORS

Support

Advice and consultation in our areas of expertise, trainings, workshops, FORS Guides

Survey mandates

Specific surveys or part(s) of surveys carried out at the request of individuals or institutions

Information

Overview of social science research in Switzerland and publications

Archiving service

Archiving service

- Database of about 11,000 social science research projects available online via FORSbase
- Overview of social science research in Switzerland
- Bibliographic resource
- Possibilities for archiving and sharing data

Data distribution

Data distribution

- Collection of more than 600 datasets documented according to international standards
- Distribution of datasets archived at FORS
- Free access to data via FORSbase

The online tool for archiving and distributing research data

Support

Data management support

Our data management vision and strategy

Early days: Focus on DM from a data service point of view

- «We want your data» perspective
- «We want you to have fun, and apply good practices» perspective

And then came the Swiss Federal Survey of Adolescents

- We got to run a large-scale survey (2013)
- We wanted to make it the best survey ever (with respect to DM)
- We failed to apply the recommendations we were teaching

Our data management vision and strategy

Early days: Focus on DM from a data service point of view

- «We want your data» perspective
- «We want you to have fun, and apply good practices» perspective

Current days: Focus on DM from a researcher's point of view

- «We want you to be able to apply good DM» perspective
- «We want you to see the value of DM for your work above all» perspective

It does not exclude data sharing or fun

- Need for more concrete guidelines and solutions
- Focus on 'day-to-day' management and re-use by the team

October 2017- our DM story takes a new turn

A new funder's policy

- Our main funder, the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) requires DMPs with all proposals.
- New requirements concern storage, sharing and archiving of data collected and produced in the course of the research project.

➡ Strong reactions from the research community ('one more administrative burden')

➡ A great opportunity for us
How to use the DMP (and forced-interest in data management) to pass on our messages?

Our vision versus funders' visions

- It is important to think beyond the declaration of intent (DMP)
- It is important to think in practical terms (operationalisation)
- Data management represents an opportunity

Our initial intention

- Develop one good DMP example
- Include post-funding guidance

What we did

- Provided assistance with DMPs
- Organised and participated in DMP events

What we learned

- There is no such thing as **one** good example
 - ➔ Instead of **one** good example, provide a reflexive model (FORS Guide)
- There are various shortcomings with the current SNSF template
- Even reluctant researchers can get to appreciate data management (plans)

Survey mandates

Dissemination of information

FORS⁺ GUIDES

to survey methods
and data management

FORS⁺ PAPERS

Working paper series

**Survey
Methods:**
Insights from the Field

Social
change
in Switzerland

Unil FORS⁺ LIVE⁵

DeFacto
BELEGT, WAS ANDERE MEINEN

News and more information

- www.forscenter.ch
- FORS Bulletin (Newsletter)
- Follow us on twitter/facebook:
[@forsresearch](https://twitter.com/forsresearch)

FORS⁺

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Data life cycle

Our activities and services cover the entire data lifecycle

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